

CERN input to the Consultation on Cloud Computing Research Innovation Challenges for WP 2018-2020

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Introduction

This document provides input from CERN to the European Commission's Consultation on Cloud Computing Research Innovation Challenges for Work Programme 2018-2020. The document identifies a series of domains impacting the use of e-infrastructures that CERN considers of high importance for the work programme and to address the three O's strategy: *Open Science, Open Innovation and Open to the world* outlined in the scoping paper entitled 'European Research Infrastructures incl. e-infrastructures'.

Open Science and Open Innovation

CERN prepared a document¹ in spring 2016 outlining its views on how to establish a pilot European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) that was provided as input to the STFC led consortium that submitted the successful INFRADEV-04-2016 proposal. The paper identified a set of overarching issues for EOSC stakeholders that need to be addressed in the work programme, including:

- the set of services to be provided and their essential features that will promote open science;
- a legal framework that must balance the interests of users and service providers while respecting relevant legislation and encouraging innovation;
- the funding and provisioning models under which services are procured, operated and used;
- the principles of consensual governance, including compliance with the legal and ethical requirements that those stakeholders are being asked to buy into.

Six months after publication, CERN considers the contents of the document still relevant and necessary for the EOSC to encourage open science and open innovation. Since the document was published, a number of issues have become more visible and merit support in the 2018-2020 work programme:

Funding data preservation

The EOSC HLEG is proposing to dedicate 5% of research funding to support open science and data preservation. The implementation of this objective will have an important impact on the data management plans of the Research Infrastructures and the 2018-2020 WP so the scope and associated funding mechanisms to implement this proposal merit further investigation.

Data Management Services

Data Management at the exascale will be a necessity for Research Infrastructures coming into operation on the timeline of 2020. Current data management tools do not scale to the required level and significant development effort will be needed to produce exascale production quality data management services and to ensure that scientific workloads can profit from exascale computing architectures in order to process such quantities of data.

¹ The European Open Science Cloud Pilot Phase, CERN, April 2016, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.50072>

Expanding the User Base

The EC communication on the European Cloud Initiative published in April 2016 highlights that the EOSC user-base will be expanded beyond scientific users to government and industry as well as integrating commercial service providers. The expansion of EOSC to these audiences and service providers will need careful preparation and hence should be an integral part of WP 2018-2020.

Procurement

Procurement of commercial cloud services has been highlighted by DG CNECT at the DI4R 2016 event in Cracow² as an important element of the EOSC. The on-going HNSciCloud Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) action and the IaaS framework agreement created by GEANT have demonstrated the interest from Research Infrastructures and commercial cloud service providers to participate in procurement activities targeting Europe's research and education community. A series of recommendations are made in the recently published PICSE roadmap³ that are directly relevant to this activity and should be considered in the planning of WP 2018-2020. While the current focus is on IaaS procurement, it is understood that this will need to expand to encompass services at the PaaS and SaaS levels, and to ensure that value chains can be established that maximise the impact on downstream industries of publicly funded research and the data produced by research infrastructures⁴.

HNSciCloud has shown that the PCP instrument can be used to incite public and commercial service providers to co-design innovative services with research organisations that satisfy the pressing needs of user communities. But as these services reach production-level operation then different funding instruments will be required. Funding instruments supporting the operational phase of the service lifecycle must provide mechanisms by which service providers can have their operating costs (potentially with profits) reimbursed to encourage a wide participation in EOSC and the sustainability of the services. Service sustainability will rely on an economic model with a flexible payment scheme that allows researchers to have *free-at-the-point-of-use* access to the services while providing a means to route money from multiple funding sources to the providers of services according to metered usage by end-users. It is essential that information about the cost of the services consumed is made available to end-users so that they can select the most cost effective services that satisfy their needs.

Open to the world

Large scale research infrastructures having global research communities affiliated to their data and scientific programmes will be essential drivers for innovative and challenging requirements for the EOSC. EOSC cannot be developed in isolation and it must interoperate with similar structures being planned in other regions of the world in order for it to be adopted by global research communities.

The Europe Open Science Cloud represents a fundamental shift in the approach to e-infrastructures and we understand that the EC would like to use WP 2018-2020 to implement this change. We agree with this strategy and believe the majority of the existing e-infrastructure consortia have yet to embrace this new model so they will need strong encouragement to enable them to make the transition. We think that positioning WP 2018-2020 to enable an 'e-Infrastructure commons marketplace'⁵ would make the message very clear and provide a catalyst for the transition. A marketplace approach to the *commons*⁶ is being implemented by the National Institute of Health in the USA and they have participated in Helix Nebula events in Europe⁷. Establishing links between such initiatives and the EOSC would be beneficial for Europe, USA and global research communities.

² <http://www.digitalinfrastructures.eu/content/opening-plenary>

³ Cloud Services Procurement Roadmap for Public Research Organisations, April 2016, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.50504>

⁴ Helix Nebula 8th General Assembly, ESA, Frascati, September 2016, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/556727/>

⁵ e-Infrastructure commons marketplace, Maryline Lengert - ESA, Bob Jones - CERN, David Foster - CERN, Steven Newhouse - EMBL-EBI, June 2014, <https://cds.cern.ch/record/1709709/files/HelixNebula-MISC-2014-001.pdf>

⁶ <https://datascience.nih.gov/commons>

⁷ Helix Nebula 7th General Assembly, EMBL, Heidelberg, January 2016, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/450560/>